

WIND ENERGY INTEGRATION EFFECTS ON THE STABILITY OF NIGERIA'S 330KV GRID

Nestor Chima Ugwoke¹ Patrick Ifeanyi Obi¹ Nnaemeka Sunday Ugwuanyi^{2,3}

^{1,2}Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture Umudike, Nigeria,

³Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, Alex Ekwueme Federal University
Ikwo, Nigeria.

⁴Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Massachusetts 02139, USA

Corresponding author's email address: nestorchima2020@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of wind energy penetration on the small signal and transient stability of the Nigerian 330kV, 50-bus power grid. Simulation results, obtained using the PSAT toolbox in MATLAB, reveal improved stability with wind energy integration, accompanied by reduced active power losses (up to 40%). Nuances in oscillation dynamics are also observed. This research contributes to the development of a reliable and resilient power grid in Nigeria, informing policy and engineering decisions on renewable energy integration.

Keywords: wind energy, small-signal stability, doubly-fed induction generator, renewable energy, power system

1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria's power sector reforms which aimed to bridge the significant gap between electricity demand and supply have failed, leaving many citizens without access to electricity. The country heavily relies on fossil fuels and has limited hydroelectric contributions (Obi *et al.*, 2021). As the population grows and energy demand increases, the supply continues to dwindle, exacerbating the crisis. The unsustainable nature of fossil fuel-based energy generation, coupled with the power sector's unreliability due to outdated infrastructure, inefficient plants, poor metering, inadequate funding, vandalism, corruption, and local content issues, underscores the need for urgent reforms and a transition to sustainable energy sources.

Researchers are actively exploring clean, safe, and renewable energy sources, notably solar and wind power, to bridge the energy gap. Despite some studies suggesting that achieving 100% renewable energy integration into the grid is unfeasible due to infrastructure constraints (Brown *et al.*, 2018), others argue that it is achievable (Narayanan *et al.*, 2019). Notably, several countries have made significant strides towards this goal, with Iceland, Paraguay, Norway, Uruguay, Costa Rica, Brazil, and Canada achieving remarkable renewable energy integration levels of 100%, 99%, 97%, 95%, 93%, 76%, and 62%, respectively (Zappa *et al.*, 2019).

Globally, wind energy is the fastest-growing large-scale renewable energy source, deployed to address energy crises and environmental concerns (Tat, 2019). With over 591 GW of installed capacity worldwide (Adetokun *et al.*, 2020), wind energy harnesses kinetic energy in airflow and is widely utilized. Nigeria boasts abundant wind energy potential (Somoye, 2023; Okedu *et al.*, 2024), with an average wind speed of 3.0 m/s and regional variations: North-West (3.88-9.39 m/s), South-West (1.77-4.5 m/s), North-Central (2.46-5.36 m/s), and South-South (3.30-4.65 m/s) (Oluleye and Adeyewa, 2016). However, other studies report differing wind speed ranges: (Mas'ud *et al.*, 2015) found 1.4-3.0 m/s in the South and 4.0-5.12 m/s in the North, while (Akuru *et al.* 2017) reported 2 m/s in the Southern coastal region and 8 m/s in the far Northern region at 50 m height. (Adedipe *et al.*, 2018) also found similar regional variations in wind speeds at 10 m height.

Despite its potential, wind energy currently has no contribution to Nigeria's national grid (Adedipe *et al.*, 2018). However, small-scale wind turbines are used for water pumping, battery charging, small-scale enterprise electrification, and experimental purposes. Notable examples include a 0.75 kW turbine in Dan Jawa Village, Sokoto State, and a 5-kW station in Sayya Gidan Gada, Sokoto State (Akuru *et al.*, 2017; Mohammed *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, the Rimi Local Government Area in Katsina State boasts a 10 MW onshore wind turbine capacity (Mohammed *et al.*, 2017). To integrate these wind energy sources into the grid and enhance power supply reliability, small signal stability analysis is essential.

Researchers have varying views on the impact of small signal stability analysis of wind energy integration on the power system. Some studies suggest that increasing wind energy penetration enhances damping of inter-area oscillations (Qi *et al.*, 2023; Hasan *et al.*, 2014), while others indicate that integrating doubly fed induction generators (DFIG) reduces the damping ratio of the power system (Essallah *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, wind turbine integration has been found to increase the damping ratio and reduce the oscillation frequency of all modes (Fuentefria *et al.*, 2019; Vangalapudi & Ravikanth, 2020). However, (Sadhana *et al.* 2017) reported that wind energy integration does not affect low-frequency oscillations in remote areas. Furthermore, some studies revealed that small signal stability improves with increasing wind farm output (Bishwasl *et al.*, 2020; Bin *et al.*, 2013). Overall, the impact of wind energy integration on small signal stability depends on the sizing and location of the wind farm, as concluded by (Mohammed *et al.*, 2020 and Arghya, 2021).

This paper investigates the impact of integrating Doubly Fed Induction Generators (DFIG) into Nigeria's 330 kV power systems on small signal stability, transient stability, and real power losses. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides the background and methodology, Section 3 presents an overview of the Nigerian power system, Section 4 discusses the results and analysis, and Section 5 concludes with recommendations for future improvements.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF WIND ENERGY INTEGRATION

This section provides a comprehensive review of the theoretical foundations of wind energy integration, essential for understanding the principles and challenges associated with incorporating wind power into the grid.

2.1 Wind turbine technology

A modern wind turbine comprises four primary components: the tower, nacelle, yaw mechanism, and rotor (Eugen, 2017; Emeghara *et al.*, 2022). These components work together to convert wind energy into electrical energy. In load flow studies, wind energy integration is modeled using various approaches, including PQ, PV, and RX-controlled models (Feijo and Cidrass, 2000). This paper focuses on the PQ model, which is particularly suited for power factor control and enables the analysis of wind energy integration in the grid.

2.2 Dynamic modeling of wind turbine

In wind energy conversion, the kinetic energy of an air mass, m , moving at a velocity, v , can be expressed as

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 illustrates a schematic of the wind power generation model. The wind turbine model represents the relationship between the mechanical power extracted from the turbine (P_{wind}) and the wind speed, which can be expressed as

$$P_{wind} = \frac{1}{2}\rho A_{wt} C_p(\lambda, \theta) v_{wind}^3 \quad (2)$$

where, ρ is the air density, A_{wt} is the wind turbine swept area, v_{wind} is the wind speed, C_p is the power coefficient, λ is the tip speed, and θ is the pitch angle.

Fig. 1: Schematic Diagram of wind turbine generator model

2.3 Small-signal stability analysis

Small-signal stability refers to the power system's ability to maintain synchronism under minor disturbances, such as small changes in load and generation. The Nigerian grid's small-signal stability has been previously studied (Ugwuanyi *et al.*, 2021a; Ugwuanyi N.S *et al.*, 2021b) but only for conventional systems without renewable energy. Small-signal stability analysis involves examining the eigenvalues and vectors of a linearized system to assess stability. This analysis is performed by representing the power system as a set of differential-algebraic equations and evaluating the eigenvalues to determine stability. Consider a power system represented by a set of differential-algebraic equations:

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u), \quad (3)$$

$$y = g(x, u), \quad (4)$$

The state variable, output variable, and input variable are denoted by x , y , and u , respectively. The vector g represents the relationship between the output and input. The system's output indicates whether the system is stable or unstable. The eigenvalues can be real, zero, or complex. Complex eigenvalues occur in conjugate pairs. A system is considered stable if all eigenvalues, λ , lie in the left half of the complex plane.

$$\lambda = \sigma \pm j\omega \tag{5}$$

The damping ratio, time constant and the frequency are given as

$$\zeta = \frac{-\sigma}{\sqrt{\sigma^2 + \omega^2}} \tag{6}$$

$$f = \frac{\omega}{2\pi} \tag{7}$$

In this paper, a damping of 5% and above is taken to be sufficient in this power system analysis.

3. The NIGERIAN 50 – BUS, 330KV POWER SYSTEM

The single-line diagram of the system, shown in Figure 2 (Ugwuanyi *et al.*, 2024a) features 14 generators, including 3 hydro-based generators - Kainji, Shiroro, and Jebba - located in the Northern region. The remaining generators are gas-fired, situated in the Southern region, proximal to gas sources. The simulation data is obtained from (Ugwuanyi *et al.*, 2024b) Egbin generating station serves as the reference generator.

Fig. 2: Single-line diagram of Nigerian 50-bus 330 kV power system

This study considers three distinct cases:

- I. **Case 1:** The base case, without the integration of DFIG into the grid network.
- II. **Case 2:** The integration of DFIG into the system, compared with the base case.

The system is modeled using PSAT, a toolbox within the MATLAB package, and the load flow analysis is performed using the Newton-Raphson method.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The load flow analysis was initially conducted for the base case (without DFIG integration) to determine active power losses, damping ratios of the slowest oscillation modes, and Critical Clearing Time (CCT). The results are presented in Table 1.

In Case 2, a DFIG-based wind turbine generator (WTG) was integrated at bus 6 (Ajah) of the Nigerian 50-bus power system. The load flow analysis was repeated to assess active power losses, damping ratios, and CCT. The results show a 40% improvement in active power losses before increasing beyond the base case, as shown in Figure 3. The small signal stability analysis reveals consistent stability for the three electromechanical modes with the lowest damping ratios, as depicted in Figure 4. To investigate transient stability, a three-phase fault was simulated at Kainji GS and Ihovbor GS, triggering local and inter-area oscillations, respectively, as per previous research (Ugwuanyi *et al.*, 2021b). The results indicate improved local oscillations with increasing integration levels, while inter-area oscillations initially improve but decline after 25% integration, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Table 1: Damping ratios of slowest modes, power loss and critical clearing time for base case

% penetration	Status	Electromechanical modes			Critical Clearing Time (s)		Real Power Losses (p.u)
		Mode 1	Mode 2	Mode 3	Ihovbor Gs	Kainji Gs	
Base case	stable	6.85	2.83	8.83	0.55	1.13	0.70374

Fig 3: Active power losses versus Percentage penetration of DFIG

Fig.4: Damping ratio versus percentage of DFIG integration

Fig. 5: Critical clearing time versus percentage of DFIG integration.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigates the effects of wind energy integration on the Nigerian 330kV power system, focusing on small signal stability analysis, transient stability via critical clearing time, and active power losses. The key findings are: i) Integration of DFIG reduces active power losses by up to 40%. ii) Small-signal stability analysis shows consistent stability of electromechanical modes with DFIG integration. iii) Local oscillations improve with increasing integration levels, while inter-area oscillations improve and then decline after 25%.

Future research should investigate the impact of incorporating FACT devices with DFIG on the Nigerian 330kV power system. Furthermore, it is recommended to conduct a comprehensive investigation of all modes, rather than solely focusing on the slowest modes, to gain a more complete understanding of the system's behavior.

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